

Employment Opportunities & Retention for Women in Information Technology Sector

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Abstract

The aim of this research is to examine the Employment Opportunities and Retention for Women in I T Sector. Data from 100 women employees has been collected from IT companies situated in Noida. The study employs qualitative and quantitative research techniques which involves the use of self-structured questionnaires and statistical techniques as T-test, descriptive analysis, Regression analysis and Cronbach's alpha. Present study reveals that decision of stay with the organisation. Marital status of a women employee does not affect her decision to stay in job. Work life balance and job security are the other reasons of looking for new job by women employees. Since the data has been collected form IT companies situated in Noida, the ability of the data to represent the entire population is reduced. The results of this study will provide insights to implement strategies to increase women employee retention in IT companies and employment opportunities.

Keywords: Women employee, Leadership, IT, Turnover, Gurugram, WLB, Job insecurity.

Classification-JEL : L52, O14

1. INTRODUCTION

The main focus of this study is to explore the employment opportunities & retention for Women in Information Technology Industry. IT industry of India gives employment to large number of employees. Sample of 100 women employees working in IT sector is used to analyze the study. Here, the employment opportunities for Women is taken as crucial because there is a large turnover found in case of women employees. Employee turnover is the reduction in number of employees, it can be volunteer or non-volunteer and vary from

industry to industry. Finance, work life balance, Career social-security and location are some reasons for this turnover. The research gap taken for this study is turnover of women employees of IT industry in Noida. only Information Technology companies are women-friendly employers in India.

Experienced and skilled employees are the assets of an organization. IT industry has the highest turnover rate of 26 percent. Employee turnover increases with a decrease in experience level. Younger employees have a tendency to switch jobs more often. Employees

contribute their skills, expertise and knowledge in the functioning of organisation. The research is expected to examine the employment opportunities and retention of women employee and practices that leads to retention in the IT industry of India.

2. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Top leadership commitment. strategic plan of the organization which is diversified, career planning, employee involvement, empowerment, promotion, flexible work timings are the factors which are important for both managers and employees to retain the employees (Twum, 2015). The major reason for quitting the current job for any employee is dissatisfaction from his current job. Dissatisfaction can be due to working conditions, lack of growth opportunities. No proper training and no fair remuneration (Kaur, 2013). Employees do not want to work in a same position. They need support, and space so that they can work freely and grow. If they are not finding this, they will look for another employer (Tech industry report, 2016). The software industry has characterized the shift to a world in which cross border flows of skilled workers have is vital to the way firms in developing and developed countries connect. Compensation and monetary factors have been keys to promote such mobility (Commander et al., 2004). Women employee turnover is higher in technology than in science and in engineering. In all cases quit rate for women is higher than it is for men. In the high-tech industry, the quit rate is more than twice as high for women than it is for men (Hewlett et al., 2008). Women managers have extremely positive effect on other women. Juniors have the impression that senior women help them a lot. Compensation and rewards should be according to employee performance and that should also be competitive enough to retain and attract employees (Twum, 2015). A survey of Indian organization reveals that 48 percent of the turnover happens because of poor relationships with the supervisors. 53 percent of the

employees in India are not satisfied with their immediate manager (Kaur, 2013). Employees in the tech industry are becoming more proactive, to know their input has the potential for the company (Tech industry report, 2016). It has been found that proportion of female managers, changes the key variables intensely. Suddenly women employees started feeling less isolated and have an easier time accessing role models. They feel more confident in discussing work life balance issues with a female manager (Hewlett et al., 2008). Research suggests that women don't always quit job basically for family concerns. They could have taken the other decision if more flexible options they had to complete their responsibilities. If a company comes to know the reason of their quitting, things can be different to handle the situation (Women in tech report, 2016).

On the basis of literature presented in the above section the following hypothesis have been developed.

H01- There is no significant association between the organisational culture and Retention.

H02- There is no relation between marital status of employment and Retention.

H03- There is no relation between the signing the bond and the employment opportunity.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The source of data is based on primary study. The Primary data has been collected from 100 women employees from Noida through questionnaires from executive and non-executive professionals working in Indian owned, multinationals, small and big companies.

4. DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

Socio demographic factors of the employees depicts 23 of the women were in 18-26 years of age and out of 100 women, 48 were single (Table -1). Out of the total respondents 77 have not signed any bond with the company (Table -2). Maximum respondents lie in the age range of 27-35.

Table 1 : Marital Status of Employees

Particulars	Marital Status		Total
	Married	Single	
Age 18 to 26	2	21	23
27 to 35	35	25	60
36 to 44	9	2	11
45+	6	0	6
Total	52	48	100

Table 2 : Signing the Bond

Particular	Total	
Have you signed any bond to get employment	No	77
	Yes	23
Total		100

Cronbach alpha technique was employed in the present study to test reliability. The value of alpha varies from 0 to 1 and satisfactory value is considered to be above 0.6 for the scale to be reliable (Cronbach, 1951). As we can see in table 3 Cronbach's alpha is .968 which indicates a high level of internal consistency for our scale.

Table 3 : Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.968	16

Table 4 represents the Values. Final column presents the value that Cronbach's alpha would be that particular item was deleted from the scale. There is no question which helps in higher Cronbach alpha after removing that particular question except question 2, even that would result in very mirror difference.

5. LINEAR REGRESSION ANALYSIS

H01 : There is no significant correlation between the organisational culture and Retention.

Table 5 provides the R and R square values. The R value represents the simple correlation and is 0.666 which indicates strong degree of correlation between organisational culture and Retention of employees. The R

square value indicates how much variation in Retention can be explained by organisational culture (independent variable). In this case, 44.4 percent variation can be explained out of total variation.

a) Values : (Constant) There is a good organisational culture, Colleagues are cooperative, Guidance and Motivation is provided by when required, Views and suggestions of employees on work related issues are openly considered, Good performance is well Recognized by the organization, The organisation gives respect and to all employees good treatment to all employees, I feel encouraged to pursue training & development opportunities, In my company culture of open & free discussion is executed well about retention of employees, Team Work and leadership Skills are promoted, Respect and Fair Treatment are received in the organisation by other employees, Disciplinary actions against employees are taken in a Humanitarian Manner, My organisation regularly congratulate employees in recognition of their efforts, Organisation value & support regarding the personal problems of the employees, I feel comfortable while dealing with my supervisor, Current job provides employees with the opportunity to both communicate well with the staff and receive recognition from them as well, My manager is competent in guiding me through difficult professional situations.

b) Dependent variable: (Intention to stay with the organization)

Table 6 indicates how well the regression equation fits the data. With 16 values the regression effect has 16 degrees of freedom. The regression effect is statistically significant where $F(16, 68):3.393, p < 0.05$ indicating that prediction of the dependent variable is accomplished better than can be done by chance. The p value of the F statistic labeled as sig. is less than 0.05, demonstrating very strong evidence that the model has a strong explanatory power of prediction. It could also be said that since the F value is significant then all the 16 variables jointly affect the dependent variable in the population.

Table 4 : Values

Responses	Scale Mean if Item Deleted	Scale Variance if Item Deleted	Corrected Item-Total Correlation	Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted
There is a good organisational culture.	72.40	374.647	.832	.966
Colleagues are cooperative.	42.66	376.094	.758	.967
Guidance and Motivation is provided by when required.	72.44	367.024	.838	.965
Views and suggestions of employees on work related issues are openly considered.	72.77	371.844	.820	.966
Good performance is well Recognized by the organization.	72.77	373.799	.776	.966
The organisation gives respect and good treatment to all employees.	72.81	368.852	.811	.966
I feel encouraged to pursue training & development opportunities.	72.80	367.690	.836	.965
In my company culture of open & free discussion is executed well about retention of employees.	72.70	366.167	.862	.965
Team Work and leadership Skills are promoted.	72.74	369.653	.824	.966
Respect and Fair Treatment are received in the organisation by other employees.	72.50	371.579	.831	.966
Disciplinary actions against employees are taken in a Huminitarian Manner.	72.50	378.590	.768	.967
My organisation regularly congratulate employees in recognition of their efforts.	72.53	374.139	.817	.966
Organisation value & support regarding the personal problems of the employees.	72.52	382.455	.547	.971
I feel comfortable while dealing with my supervisor.	72.53	370.746	.838	.965
Current job provides employees with the opportunity to both communicate well with the staff and receive recognition from them as well.	72.79	370.550	.828	.966
My manager is competent in guiding me through difficult professional situations.	72.53	371.074	.792	.966

Table 5 : Calculations

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.666 ^a	.444	.313	1.139

Ho2: There is no relation between marital status of employees and Retention.

Table 7 shows group statistics for

independent sample t-test that was conducted to compare the Leadership composite score for single and married women employees. The results showed there was no significant difference in scores for single (M:77 .48, SD:20.40) and married women employees (M:77 .65, SD:2C.62).

The independent samples t-test was chosen as the statistical measure for this question. Results of the Levene's test indicated

Table 6 : ANOVA

Model	Residual	Regressoin	Total
Sum of Squares	70.476	88.277	158.753
df	16	68	84
Mean Square	4.405	1.298	
F	3.393		
Sig.	.000		

Table 7 : Group Statistics

	Marital Status	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Leadership composite score	Single	31	77.4839	20.40404	3.66467
	Married	60	77.6500	20.63552	2.66403

Table 8 : Independent Samples T Test

		Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means						
		F	Sig.	t	df	Sig (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std Error Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
									Lower	Upper
Leadership composite Score	Equal variances assumed	.015	.903	-.037	89	.971	-.16613	4.54716	-9.20124	8.86899
	Equal variances not assumed			-.037	61.371	.971	-.16613	4.53066	-9.22464	8.89238

that equal variances could be assumed and an alpha level of .05 was chosen for this test. The p-value of Levene's test is 0.903 we can assume that the variance of two groups is the same. (If the p-value of Levene's test is less than 0.05, we have to use the "Unequal variance" result), since the p-value is 0.971, we accept the null hypothesis and conclude that there is no difference between the mean score of leadership in marital status at 5 percent significance level

H03: There is no relation between the signing the bond and the employment opportunities.

Table 9 shows group statistics of independent sample t-test that was conducted to compare the Leadership composite score for

employees who signed bond with the company and who did not. The results showed there was no difference in scores for who signed the bond (M:7 5.42, SD: 1 7.54) and who did not sign the bond (M:78. 16, SD:21 .21).

The independent samples t-test was chosen as the statistical measure for this question. Results of the Levene's test indicated that equal variances could be assumed and an alpha level of .05 was chosen for this test. The p-value of Levene's test is 0.86j we can assume that the variance of two groups is the same. (If

Table 9 : Group Statistics

	Have you signed any bond to get employment	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Leadership composite	Yes	23	75.4211	17.54460	4.02501
	No	77	78.1667	21.21652	2.50039

the p-value of Levene's test is less than 0.05, we have to use the "Unequal variance" result), since the p-value is 0.605, we accept the null hypothesis and conclude that there is no difference between the mean score of leadership in bond signing status at 5 percent significance level.

6. CONCLUSION

It is very difficult to retain the dissatisfied employees. Present study reveals that decision

Table 10 : Independent Samples T Test

		Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means						
		F	Sig.	t	df	Sig (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std Error Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
									Lower	Upper
Leadership composite Score	Equal variances assumed	.030	.863	-.519	89	.605	-2.74561	5.29422	-13.26512	7.77389
	Equal variances not assumed			-.519	33.315	.566	-2.74561	4.73842	-12.38254	6.89131

of staying with the job depends on the relationship with the manager as well as with the organisation. Marital status of a women employee does not affect her decision to get a job. Interview with the respondents has

revealed that lack of financial rewards is the primary reason for non-retention. Work life balance and job insecurity are the other reasons of looking for new job. Work life balance is also the reason women employee quit their job.

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